

Formation of 3-oxo-5-phenylimino-1,2,4-thiadiazolidine and the related compounds :

Details of a typical experiment (where R = R' = Hydrogen) are as follow :

Carbamide (3.0 g) was suspended in chloroform (10 ml) and to this was added a chloroform solution of S-chloro-N-phenyl isothiocarbamoyl chloride (11.0 g). The reaction mixture was refluxed over a boiling water bath for 4 hr. During the reaction evolution of hydrogen chloride was noticed. The resultant solid was filtered and washed several times with chloroform followed by petroleum ether (3.2 g) and crystallised from aq. ethanol, m.p. 110° (Found : C 49.2, H 3.5, N 21.33, S 16.38. C₈H₇N₃SO requires ; C 49.74, H 3.62, N 21.76, S 16.58%). It was identified as a 3-oxo-5-phenylimino-1,2,4-thiadiazolidine (Ia) on the basis of following facts :

The product was stable to 8% boiling aq. alkali and conc. hydrochloric acid. It did not desulphurise when boiled with alkaline plumbite solution. On thermal decomposition the odours of phenylisothiocyanate and ammonia were quite perceptible. The product (1 g) on reaction with aniline (2 ml) in boiling ethanolic medium 1,3-diphenyl carbamide and 1,3-diphenyl carbamide, m.p. 152° and 235° respectively, have been isolated. The product could not be degraded with boiling alcoholic ammoniacal hydrogen sulphide of moderate concentration. IR spectrum of the product clearly indicated the presence of NH (3310 cm⁻¹), C=O (1660 cm⁻¹), C=N (1570 cm⁻¹), C—S (780 cm⁻¹) bands.

When the reaction of S-chloro-N-phenyl isothiocarbamoyl chloride was extended to phenyl carbamide, 1,3-diphenyl carbamide, 1-phenyl-3-*p*-tolyl and 1-phenyl-3-*p*-Cl-phenyl carbamides under the identical reaction conditions the related substituted 1,2,4-thiadiazolidines (Ib-Ie) have been isolated. These have been listed in Table 1.

TABLE 1—3-Oxo-5-Phenylimino-1,2,4-thiadiazolidine and its Aryl, Substituted Analogues

Reaction Conditions : Refluxing chloroform medium. S-Chloro-N-Phenyl isothiocarbamoyl chloride taken about 0.05 mole.			
Sl. No.	Carbamide (g)	1,2,4-thiadiazolidine(I) (g, m.p. °C)	IR Characteristics (cm ⁻¹)
1.	Carbamide (3 g)	3-Oxo-5-phenylimino-(Ia) (2 g), 110°	NH (3310), C=O (1660), C=N (1570)
2.	Phenyl- (6 g)	3-Oxo-4-phenyl-5-phenylimino-(Ib), (5 g), 954°	NH (3340), C=O (1670), C=N (1620)
3.	1,3-Diphenyl- (10 g)	3-Oxo-2,4-diphenyl-5-phenylimino-(Ic), (13.2 g), 345°	C=O (1660), C=N (1630)
4.	1-Phenyl-3- <i>p</i> -tolyl- (11 g)	3-Oxo-2-phenyl-4- <i>p</i> -tolyl-5-phenylimino-(Id) (11.2 g), 334°	C=O (1640), C=N (1560)
5.	1-Phenyl-3- <i>p</i> -Cl-phenyl- (11 g)	3-Oxo 2- <i>p</i> -Cl-phenyl-4-phenyl-5-phenylimino-(Ie) (14.5 g), 295°	C=O (1720), C=N (1640)
All the compounds exhibited consistent C, H, N and S analysis.			

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